

A mechanism-based reaction-diffusion model for frontal polymerization (FP): Toward rapid prediction of FP macro-observables

**Regenerative Energy-Efficient
Manufacturing of Thermoset
Polymeric Materials**

Donald Bistri

Postdoctoral Research Associate

Beckman Institute for
Advanced Science and Technology
University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign

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On the application of thermosetting polymers and composites: Perspective and Limitations

Projected Market Value

Study by Market Research Future [Article](#)

Limitations

Manufacturing – Labor and Capital Intensive

Autoclave for curing large composite structures

Heated mold for wind turbine blades

Kim et al. Composites Part A, (2019)

Energy Efficiency –

Large continuous energy input

Recyclability –

Lack of end-of-life strategies

Covalent network in thermosets limits ability to deconstruct/recycle

Bloomberg (2020) [Article](#)

Aerospace and Defense

Wind Energy

Transportation

Electronics

↑ > 3% → 0 – 3%

[1] Timmis, Andrew J., et al. The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment 20 (2015).

[2] Witik, Robert A., et al. Journal of Cleaner Production 29

Frontal Ring-Opening Polymerization: An energy-efficient self-sustaining polymerization route

 Monomer + Latent Catalyst

 Polymer

Ring-opening energy release mechanism

- Requirements
 - Low rate of reaction at initial temperature
 - Very high rate of exothermic reaction at higher temperature
 - Rate of heat production \gg rate of heat loss

Robertson et al. Nature (2018)

Curing a 10 cm X 20 cm panel in 2 min

FP Modeling: Phenomenological Reaction-Diffusion Models

$$\begin{cases} \kappa \nabla^2 T + \rho H_r \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} = \rho C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \\ \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} = A \exp\left(-\frac{E}{RT}\right) g(\alpha) \end{cases}$$

Challenges

- Coupled multi-physics equations
- Nonlinear, transient
- Sharp gradients in temperature and degree of cure in vicinity of propagating front

Convection-Driven Instabilities

Gao et al., PRL (2023)

Mechanically-Driven Surface Patterning

Kumar et al., JMPS (2023)

$$\theta = \frac{T - T_0}{T_{max} - T_0}$$

$$T_{max} = T_0 + \frac{H_r}{C_p}$$

Direct-Ink Write

Kumar et al., AM (2024)

FP Modeling: Phenomenological Model Limitations

$$\begin{cases} \kappa \nabla^2 T + \rho H_r \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} = \rho C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \\ \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} = A \exp\left(-\frac{E}{RT}\right) g(\alpha) \end{cases}$$

Chemically non-predictive owing to its empirical nature and application to a **single resin formulation**

Time costly due to strict reliance on multiple DSC data (~ 30 minutes/DSC test)

Limited utility, **one-way experiments-to-simulations workflow**.

FP Modeling: A three-step mechanism-based reaction-diffusion model

Active Initiator Production

Step 1 : Dissociation of the inhibitory ligand

$$[AI+] = -\frac{[AI_0] + [PR_3^0] + K_{eq}}{2} + \frac{1}{2}\sqrt{([AI_0] + [PR_3^0] + K_{eq})^2 - 4([AI_0][PR_3^0] - K_{eq}[II]_0)}$$

Step 2 : Single ring-opening of monomer

Step 3 : Chain growth polymerization

$$\frac{d[C]}{dt} = A_i \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{E_i}{RT}\right) [AI][1 - \alpha]$$

$$[M_0] \frac{d\alpha}{dt} = A_p \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{E_p}{RT}\right) [C][1 - \alpha]$$

FP Modeling: A three-step vs. Phenomenological Model Performance

Polymerization front velocity over a large range of compositions

Polymerization front velocity with change in both resin composition and processing conditions

Frontal Polymerization Morphogenic Patterning: From the lens of a mechanism-based model

Emergent behavior in numerous natural systems is attributed to competing reaction-transport phenomena, giving rise to symmetry breaking events.

Biological Matter

Animal Skin Markings

Nature

Sand Ripples, Cloud Patterns

Material Science

*Phase-Separating
Materials*

*Oscillatory chemical
reactions*

*“The chemical
basis of
morphogenesis”
A.M. Turing
(1951)*

Frontal Polymerization Morphogenic Patterning: From the lens of a mechanism-based model

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Animal Skin Mar

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Can we explore similar concepts to produce emergent behavior in FP – synthetic materials?

Material Science

Phase-Separating Materials

Oscillatory chemical reactions

*“The chemical basis of morphogenesis”
A.M. Turing
(1951)*

Frontal Polymerization Morphogenic Patterning: A time lapse

Open mold spontaneous patterning: Study by Loyd et al. (ACS Central Science, 2021)

Limited understanding of the controlling mechanisms

Controlled patterning by frontal polymerization: Study by Paul et al. (Nature, 2024)

Time

Controlled patterning by frontal polymerization: Study by Paul et al. (Nature, 2024)

Increased propensity for patterning

Can we provide a mechanistic-guided understanding behind these observations?

On the origins of emergent behavior in frontally-polymerized systems: A mechanism-based model guided understanding

$$[AI^+] = -\frac{[AI_0] + [PR_3^0] + K_{eq}}{2} + \frac{1}{2}\sqrt{([AI_0] + [PR_3^0] + K_{eq})^2 - 4([AI_0][PR_3^0] - K_{eq}[II]_0)}$$

Increased propensity for emergent behavior

$$K_{eq} = \exp\left(-\frac{dH^\circ}{RT} + \frac{dS^\circ}{R}\right)$$

Different ligand substituents alter the dissociation thermodynamics

On the origins of emergent behavior in frontally-polymerized systems: A mechanism-based model guided understanding

$$K_{eq} = \exp\left(-\frac{dH^o}{RT} + \frac{dS^o}{R}\right)$$

Different ligand substituents alter the dissociation thermodynamics

These results seem to point to the presence of an inhibition-limited dissociation equilibrium

activation/supply

$$[AI^+] = -\frac{[AI_0] + [PR_3^0] + K_{eq}}{2} +$$

$$\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{([AI_0] + [PR_3^0] + K_{eq})^2 - 4([AI_0][I_0])}$$

A systematic exploration of the hypothesis

If the hypothesis is to hold true, *a saturation front velocity must be attained with decreasing monomer loading (i.e., increasing inhibitor concentration)*

Specialize for a COD monomer + Ru-1 baseline demonstration

← Increasing inhibitor + initiator

A systematic exploration of the hypothesis

If the hypothesis is to hold true, *a saturation front velocity must be attained with decreasing monomer loading* (i.e., increasing inhibitor concentration)

Specialize for a COD monomer + Ru-1 baseline demonstration

But existing literature states that patterns arise close to front quenching...

← Increasing inhibitor + initiator

Experimental map of emergent behavior as a function of composition

! This work

Expanded Design Envelope

Ability to pattern + Good Curing Speeds

COD

+

Ability to map emergent behavior over a wide range of compositions + processing conditions

Simulations performed in open-source FEniCS platform

Mapping Emergent Behavior with Variation in Resin Chemistry

$$K_{eq} = \exp\left(-\frac{dH^0}{RT} + \frac{dS^0}{R}\right)$$

A roadmap for controlling emergent behavior by precise control of chemistry

Summary

1. Developed a **mechanism-based reaction-diffusion framework** to model the coupled three-step sequence of FROMP reaction kinetics.
2. Demonstrated the capacity of the framework to **capture macroscopic FROMP observables** (i.e., front velocity, maximum front temperature, front propagation mode) **over a wide range of compositions + processing conditions**
3. Numerically informed *a novel paradigm for emergent behavior in frontally-polymerized synthetic materials* with spatially varying mechanical properties.
4. Demonstrated the ability to **map emergent behavior over a wide range of compositions + processing conditions**

Thank you for your attention!
Happy to take any questions

AMS Group, Beckman Institute

Computational Solid Mechanics Group

